
Socio-Economic development in Tehsil Alipur

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Abstract

According to modern concept of philosophy of history presented by the historian like Voltaire and Marx that history is the study of human progress. This progress might be observed in different region as per the availability of economic sources. Economic development is considered very important for socio-political stability of the country. This is a micro level study of a region which presents a picture for the state. Many economic developments can be seen during British era. The economy of the Tehsil depends upon agriculture which is based on riverine system. New British Government introduced many agricultural reforms and new methods of cultivation and irrigation, hence total production of land was increased. They introduced new sources of communication, transportation. They made new settlements through them Government revenue had increased. This Paper primarily deals to explore the condition of the economic development in the Tehsil Alipur from (1929 to 1971).

Keywords: History, Human Progress, Economic, Development, Pakistan, Tehsil, Alipur etc.

Introduction

Alipur is Tehsil headquarter and it has great economic importance in the economy of the District Muzaffargarh because it is a riverine estate. After the creation of Pakistan Alipur Tehsil became the part of Multan Division as a Tehsil of District Muzaffargarh, Government gave special attention to improve its economic condition, so Government provided many facilities to increase the level of living. There was no electricity in the year 1962, availability of the Electricity was possible in the Alipur in 1964, and the waterworks arrangements are completed in 1970. Through new economic developments by the Government of Pakistan the progress of the Tehsil has improved, due to modern skills of cultivation and use of fertilizer production of the Tehsil has increased.

Social Development

A process of change that happened in the society is called social development which indicates to advance society. When British came here they introduced new administrative structure of centralization, which was colonial system. They imposed new fundamental laws in every field. They established new administrative centers in the place of old; Ali Pur was also included in new administrative system of British. By this cause there were happened many changes in every field of society. People's life style their education, Religion, language, health, their traditions customs and structure of caste and tribe were also affected very much. All these changes were happened in every field of society, due to these changes society was much

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developed and structure of demography is society was also changed.

“Social theory can be defined as the theory of scientific ways of thinking about social life. It encompasses ideas about how societies change and develop, about Method of explaining social behavior, about power and social Modernity and civilization, revolution and structure, class and gender authenticity, utopias and memurious other concept and problems in social life”¹.

Society based on a group of people, who are socially connected with each other. They are united for the Purpose of discussion as about social issues like health, education, Laws, they also discussed their daily life social affair and Business issues. Through this Interaction of people have developed their confidence. Their Moral values are improved through this social interaction they are also promoted traditions and friendly manners.

What is Economic development?

The term “economic development” is a process of change in national income over time. “Economic growth and “economic development” are a little change in both by definition and by compilation. Economic growth means more in output per capita. While, economic development implies both of more output and change in technical and institutional arrangements by which it is produced. Further, growth may simply not only more output but also “more output and more efficiency, i.e., increased unit in input”.²

The economic development means a process of change in which an economy is measured by input and output. The input in which investor invests money and in output he receives profit as a results. So, input and output are a process of change which reflects increase income in per capita, and then, through this process an investor estimated his expenditures, profit, comforts and luxuries of life.

People Occupations and their Economic condition.

The economic development of any area depends upon some fundamental resources such as agriculture, Industries, Livestock and forests, Fisheries. Economically Alipur Tehsil is an important area of the District Muzaffargarh by agriculture and agricultural products, but due to the insufficient facilities it was not very progressive. In the Tehsil Alipur, famous and honorable occupations are agriculture Livestock and Fisheries. During the British era mostly Muhammadans were the agriculturists and Hindus were the Merchants money landers and traders but 80% economy of the region based on agriculture.

All occupations depended upon agriculture such as Tarkhan (carpenter), Julahas (weavers), Mochies (shoe makers) and Nai (barber); all were dependent upon agriculture. The term Olak was used for all of those persons who engaged to above all professions and were also called Olakee and they received little amount in the return of their services from landlords. It is common that they received wheat one mound per year. There were no regular classes of field laborers so the people were too poor. According the survey report of J. W. Thomas (1935), if the laborer was employed in harvesting, they get two ‘Annas’ and supplement with the gift of one seer (Kg) Gurr.³

When British came there they introduced many economic developments, they introduced new departments as agriculture department, forests, livestock etc and to run them they need many people. Through these developments the means of employment were increased and as

well as economic condition of people had improved, and material status was highly. Therefore after the establishment of new state of Pakistan people faced many difficulties economically, but the Government of Pakistan soon find out the solution of these difficulties. Government introduced modern technology and then people cultivated their lands with new technology.

Livestock is another important source of the economy of the Alipur Tehsil; it is an old and very common occupation of the people. The large numbers of population in the Tehsil Alipur belong to the Villages and their majority was farmers. Every famer had his own team of bullocks for his help in the fields to thrash the crops. Livestock fulfill the needs of meat better, eggs and Milk. Common animals in the Tehsil are Buffaloes, Cows, Sheep, and Goats. Camels; Donkeys were also used for transportation. Veterinary hospital was established in 1969 and it started its work in 1970, before this it was an ordinary dispensary.⁴ Agricultural profession has much developed between the years 1960-1970. According to the report of 1972 the position of Livestock department was as;

Year	Area	Bullock s oxen	Cows	Buffaloe s	Cow Buffaloe s	Youn g Stock	Agri.Stoc k	Shee p Goats	Camel s
1903	Alipu r	43972	42830	800	18186	25384	128172	86279	898
1920	Alipu r	46422	41951	636	15168	42362	145569	73952	649
1923	Alipu r	46702	404204	682	14021	34254	136093	73076	984
1960	Alipu r	42243	155076	42243	17084	53555	2768
1971	Alipu r	4200	197048	94762	88100	4600
1981	Alipu r	42876	19955	9632	1943	35982	..	91547	4617

The condition of livestock was very poor due to the lack of dairy farming only villagers adopt this occupation; breeding facilities are much affected by increasing population. Mostly people have interest in export items for the Punjab Market; they kept breed animals in which horses, donkeys, Cows Goats and ox, Poultry.⁵

Trade and Commerce

Agriculture was common in the Tehsil Ali Pur but manufacturing things made here by men. Trade and commerce started here when British introduced railway system in the District Muzaffargarh in 1886 and this was a good step towards extend the economy of the Tehsil. The chief trade products in the Tehsil were gurr, sugarcane cotton, wheat, ghee, dates, mangoes, indigo and snuff. The cultivators sold these things to dealers of small town, and they again passed them to the export merchants'. Through the opening of railway the trade made easier for everyone and railway stations were used as the center of trade, grain was brought to Muzaffargarh to Ali Pur and Karor to Muzaffargarh. This new trade system removed the

old riverine trade. Long vehicles introduced in 1945 trade was also become more easier and by this facility trade was increased.⁶

Major products

Ali Pur is an agricultural city and its major agricultural products were wheat, cotton, sugarcane, rice, barley, maize, bajra, indigo, and pomegranate. Wheat and cotton were harvested in a large land. The total average of crops production 0.036 in 1861 and rainfall condition was high i.e. 4.71 mm. So, the crops were damaged through high rainfall.⁷ Due to this reason, the prices were very high, the wheat was sold RS. 12/- per muand and rice price was Rs. 10/- per muand. In the year 1893, the average rainfall recorded 2.73 mm and average production was 4.36% and prices were so low because of good condition of crops due to this, the health condition was increased. Deaths were not seen and birth ratio had increased. Between 1894 -1900, rainfall average was 2.67 mm and crops condition was good, thus, their prices were going to low. Wheat was sold Rs. 7-8 per muand and gurr was sold at Rs. 3/- per muand.⁸

There is no record of Tehsil products since 1901 to 1930; it is only available at district level. If we see the District record of 1936, the total agricultural products were very high and rainfall condition was low. According to the Administration report of Public works department (irrigation branch 1933-34), total wheat average was 11.6 muand per acre and price which realized by cultivators was Rs. 2.1/- per muand and value of outturn primary produce per acre cols. Rs. 22 and value of secondary produce per acre Rs. 4/-. The value of standing crops per acre was Rs. 26/-. Gram per acre in muands 9.8, its value of out-turn was per acre RS.2, value of standing crops was per acre RS.18.⁹

Cotton *Desi* its price per acre in muands 4.5 and its normal percentage per acre in muands was 120 and price realized by cultivator per muand 4.0, value of primary cotton per muands was 22 rupees and value of standing crop was also same. American cotton percentage of per acre was 110 and its primary produce price was 4.6 and its secondary and standing price was 24 per acre. Sugarcane to estimate normal per acre in muands was 23.7 and its standing value was per acre 81 rupees. Rice production was estimated per acre in muands 18.3 and it's secondly and standing value Rs. 23 per acre.¹⁰

So we can easily understand the condition of products, desi cotton and sugarcane produce was very high compare to American cotton and gram, rice produce also good. In the year 1936 the rainfall average was normal and December 1935 to October 1936 normal rainfall was harvesting 1.88 inches.¹¹

This was benefited for crops and grazing land. Crops condition was remain very good throughout the year on both kinds of soil. Canals were running with sufficient water¹². In the Tehsil Ali Pur rainfall average was threatened 2.38 and this was dangerous for standing crops. Peas and turnip etc were in growth progress and the condition of rice was harvested. Because of high rain fall the crops was damaged and their prices were increased. Green fodder and grazing were available. Both Rivers were running low and Indus canal was running with sufficient water supplies. In the last ten year the condition of crops was very good.¹³, rain fall record was nil in the Tehsil. Canal supply water was running with sufficient water. Their prices were not high such as wheat per muand 9 rupees and cotton 12 rupees per muand. In the 1940 year harvesting rainfall was recorded 1.03 and it proved good for standing crops.¹⁴

At the Tehsil level this was 0.03. In month of July gurr prices were 5 rupees per muand. In the year 1947 the country was under political crises and prices of things were under ups and downs but their produce was good. Wheat was sale 10 -7-10 rupees per muand and cotton prices were 7-12-10 per muand, barely was sale 6-10-8 October to November.¹⁵ In the month of December there was no rainfall was counted and standing crops condition was very good. Bajra and Jawar were harvested with normal out turns. Conditions of castles were satisfactory and public health was good. The canal series of Chenab was closed and Sindh canals were running with enough water supplies.¹⁶ Wheat rice, gurr and cotton were major products and their total sale was record 80% in different Town in the Tehsil Ali Pur, it was flooded area and its crops were much affected by a flood that is why its economy was very low compare to Multan city.¹⁷

After the creation of Pakistan the cash product is cotton and it is an important crop of the Tehsil, cotton of Alipur is very famous in the whole country. Cotton is not only use for the manufacturing clothes but it also used for the preparation many other products. There are two form of cotton cultivated, American quality of cotton and Desi quality of cotton. It exports to other foreign countries.¹⁸

Cottage Industries

According to the Industrial point of view Alippur is much backward area. Before the creation of Pakistan the Tehsil had few cottage industries. Mostly cottage Industries improved in the Tehsil during the British era. Cotton weaving was very common in the Tehsil Ali Pur. Mostly the white clothes were weaved sometime blue color was mixed, yellow and red strips also weaving in the sides of dupattas and pakas. There were no silk weaving industries in the tehsil. There was no carpet industry in the district but in the tehsil darries and carpets khess were manufactured in the village Jahan Pur. Khadi work was very common.

The major manufacture was snuff that was manufactured in the village Parmat not only in previous centuries but it is still prepared snuff at a large scale now a days and export to Sakkhar and Bahawalpur. Taddi (Mate) and basket making was another work it prepared with date leaves, it was a common profession both in Hindus and Muahammadans. In the north bank of Indus trunks (toing) and waste paper baskets Murras (A thing like chair) large quantities were prepared.

Kuppeis (Canes) were prepared for ghee and oil in 1929 in Khair Pur Sadat, but with the arrival of British these things were changed they introduced tin and plastic things that killed old fashion things¹⁹. At the time of partition of 1947 there was no any development seen at Industrial level in the whole tehsil. In the year 1960 the small scale cottage industries started their production. In the Tehsil Alipur there were two flooring Mills? But now there are eleven flour mills after 1990.

Means of communication and transportation

There were no specific means of communication, and few bullock carts used in the Tehsil. Camels horses and donkeys were used for travel and loading. When British came first they measured the lands and to construct the roads. Ali Pur to Muzaffargarh 27 miles metaled roads between Muzaffargarh to Ghazi Ghat 20 miles metaled road and 6 miles between Chenab. Sher sultan to south of Muzaffargarh 27 miles metaled road. There were ten 2nd class

roads in the Tehsil as Jatoi to Ali Pur, Ali Pur to Khair Pur and Sher sultan to Jatoi and Khair Pur to Mudwala etc.

In year the 1886 Sindh sager branch of North West Railway built by British which entered in the District through the Chenab bridge famous as Shershah and run through the northern half of the district, turning northwards along east of the Indus. Its one line had been surveyed from Muzaffargarh to Punjnad and Dera Nawab via Ali Pur Tehsil. In the 1939 there was run a small kind of train called Thela it carried two men and other two or three men paused it. Tangas and Motor Lorries were used for traveling.

The British Government introduced System of post first time in 1857. After the independence war they established here a strong postal system. The postal head office was in Muzaffargarh under the supervision of post office superintendent. In the Tehsil Ali Pur four sub postal offices. Telegraph head office and sub offices were worked all together, at Sher sultan Jatoi and Seet Pur telegraph offices used for official purpose. All these developments can be seen during British period.²⁰

In those days post office was an important source of communication. According to the census of 1972 in the district there were 224 post office and 1647 telephone connections and 2 telegraph offices, but in the tehsil Ali pur there were 13 post offices in 1960²¹. Another source of communication was radio and newspaper only 20% of total population has access to the radio and newspaper. Local press of Ali Pur introduced after 1975, but for national and international information newspaper of Multan Lahore used. Television also introduced after 1980.²²

But in the year 1947 there were no any moter buses and car, only 49 Vehicles registered in the District Muzaffargarh. In the Ali Pur Tehsil large numbers of tanggas were also seen in different towns in 1949. Moter buses and trucks used in pakka roads there were 2/3 buses running in the tehsil and car was in use of few people. After 1970 this strength was increased.²³

List of people who have vehicles in 1945-50

Qazi Muhammad Panah son of Fareed Bakhsh Ali Pur	LTV	23-10-1945
Qazi Muhammad Nwaz son of Fareed Bakhsh Ali Pur	LTV	23-10-1945
K.B. Makhdum Honorary Magistrate in Seet Pur	---	02-12-1946
Ghulam Qadir Khan Phullan	Motor cycle	22-8-1847
Malik Sher Muhammad son of Malik Roshan Ghaloo	Car	06-02- 1949
Qazi Khuada Bakhsh son of Ghulam Rasool Ali pur	Car	06-02-1950

Aspects of Physical history

If we examined the physical features of the Tehsil Ali Pur it divided into two parts, one is called paka and other is bett. One is that where floods are very highy and there is no scene of any crops and second is that where floods are less violent. The climate of the Alipur is dry and hot in summer, usually heat recorded in summer season about 42 or 45 degree and in winter cold. Rainfall condition was June to September 4.13 and October to December 1.48 inch

recorded. There was no any geological place except it there were different kind of trees, rivers and canals. These were the famous trees found in the Alipur as dalbergiya or sisal in local language called talhi, kikar sharen jaal were long lush green trees in a large number. kanda awk calligonum, lai were found. Fruit trees like desi ber and Arabic date trees mango and falsa lassorra and pomegrante trees were common in everywhere in the Tehsil Alipur.

Forests:

In the Tehsil Ali Pur four forests were very popular and situated 40 to 75 miles from railway station and 6 miles in the east of Ali Pur. These were the big and thick forests, china malana was the one of the best forest one of them and was situated about 6 miles to the south west of Bakiani and it was flooded every year its total area was 4180 acre. There were fine patches of trees; third part of this forest was normally dry and unsuitable. The forest of damarwala was second big forest with 3069 acre area and situated on the right bank of the river Chenab distinct away 2 miles from the main stream. It had combination of all type of trees and there were a fine belt of kikar trees, the half western side of the forest was sandy and there was mostly found kana grass and poplar, its seven hundred acres were burnt on west side but large part of forest was remaining safe.

Forest of Bet Diwan Sahib was distinct away 25 miles from the south west of the Ali Pur and was near to Indus River and near about in 1922 or 1923 its large portion was washed away except 300 acres out of 3165 acres. Bakaini forest was well known in the region its total area was 1997 acres and situated in the northern area of Ali Pur and its eastern part was dry and sandy and it was not suitable for poplar growth. Only three hundred acres contained on woods and its large portion affected by floods every year. Rest house of Bet Wariyan was to close it. Forest department made by the British government in 1880. So all forest were took under the charge of forest officer in Multan division, Diwan Ram Nath kashyap appointed as divisional forest officer by government.²⁴

In these forests several kinds of animals were found in large number as, wolves, in local language called Naharrs were found in many numbers in the Tehsil. Same as wild bear was very common on the Indus banks and deer called Pahra and those deer that were found in the riverine sides called Hiran, chankarra. Jackles and foxes were common in those forests.²⁵

Rakhs under forest department in 1960 in the Tehsil Alipur;

SR.No:	Name of Rakh	Area in acers	Range
21.	Bet Diwan Sahib	3164	Ali pur
22.	Damarwala	2612	Do
23.	Mudwala	423	Do
24.	Ali pur	318	Do
25.	Khairiwala	987	Do
26.	Aliwali	4629	Do
27.	Latti.Marri	715	Do
28.	Giri	1312	Do
29.	Khanwah	1695	Do
30.	Parara	588	Do
31.	Dhaka	2302	Do
32.	Sultan pur	536	Do

Chahi	Chahi nehri	Chahi jhalari	Nehri	Jhalari	Chahi sialabi	Sialabi	Barani	Abi	Nehri abi
167	7089	27	48811	8	13055	56394	----	7331	4086
33.		Khannani			720			Do	
34.		Mission			702			Do	
35.		Langarwah			865			Do	
36.		Thal.Reg. Raj			701			Do	
37.		Kohar.Piruan			538			Do	
38.		Chandia			168			Do	
39.		Sarki			588			Do	
40.		Kotli.Lal			603			Do	
41.		Baqer.Shah			1341			Do	
42.		Mohib.Shah			628			Do	
43.		Khairpur			1014			Do	
44.		Tiba.Noor gopang			564			Do	

Classification of Soil.

As we know that Ali Pur is the riverine city and its soil condition was very poor due to Indus floods, some parts were sandy and infertile. There were different varieties of soil but its soil's classification had always been the method of irrigation. System of classification properly invented by British. For the revenue purpose they distributed lands into different classes as (1) Chahi, (2) Nehri, (3) Sailabi, (4) Chahi-nehri, (5) Chahi sailabi, (6) Abi, (7) Brani. Chahi and nehri land was considered as same. At the time of first settlement the total area of district was 301927 acres out of which 287913 acres area was suitable for cultivation chai nehri and nehri proportion were 15 to 13. In the year 1929 total cultivated area in acres were 44413 but 29475 acres having with good crops.²⁶

Chahi Nehri and Nehri proportions were 11 to 12 matured. Chahi saib and sailabi lands much affected by floods there were no arrangements to stop the floods. Total areas Chahi sailabi and both were 299062 acres and cultivated area which of them was 282338 acres. In those days price of land was 6 annas per acre.²⁷

The total cultivated area of Tehsil in acres was 587445, 27255 Acers land was under forests, 113872 Acers was not suitable for cultivation and available land for cultivation was 15893 and other land was 229675 acers in 1960.²⁸

System of irrigation and cultivation:

The system of cultivation and irrigation were same in the whole Tehsil. Before annexation the sources of watering were only rivers and canals which were dug up in different periods. In the Tehsil Ali Pur agricultural season started at the end of April when hills snow was start to melt and Canals and Rivers were full of water. Rice transplanted in these days and cotton and bajra were sown in the month of July. In the month of august sugarcane and wheat begun to plough because canals were flowing with full supply. Wheat rice gram fodder and cane were sowing in summer rain. People were waited rain for planted their crops. The proper

irrigation system was introduced by British government in 1886. The well was the main source of irrigation and cultivation. The total numbers of wells in the Tehsil were 4650. They introduced a system of two oxen well running. Every farmer had two couple of ox. Through this system of wells Cultivation was possible throughout the year and crops quantity was increased. At the time of settlement an increase of wells had been made to meet a decreased canal supply in the north of Alipur And in the south of the Tehsil good improvement could be seen along the Suleman canal. The result was that 60% area of land was able to crops. There were two kinds of wells as kacha khuh and pakka khuh and all wells worked by Persian wheels. Adhalpi system that was an agreement between land owner and tenant. The cultivator of 15 acres land needed he two yoke of oxen. British introduced drill system for sowing seeds.²⁹

After the creation of Pakistan total wells were 6153 in which of them 4650 were in use and 1053 were not in use. Irrigation system introduced properly in 1939 but it was canceled in few days. Government of Pakistan launched a project of irrigation in 1953, head Tounsa built in 1958. There was large number of land wasted due to floods, to control this situation Government of Pakistan started scarp tube well scheme in 1960. Through this scheme Government established many tube wells in different Towns of the Tehsil. This scheme completed in 1971 and now in the whole Tehsil 1095 tube wells were working.³⁰

Regular Settlements:

After annexation there were made three summary settlements in the District Muzaffargarh. The first settlement summary discusses the average collection of the Diwan Sawan Mal's regime. The 2nd settlement contained on three different assessments. Same as the 3rd settlement summary relating to the re-measurement of lands and re-correction of record preparation of Maps.

The first Regular Settlement Summary:

The first regular settlement conducted by Mr. Obrien in 1870-78 in the district Muzaffargarh and in Leah by Mr. Tucker in 1872-78. The assessment worked admirably in the year between 1880-1900. All land of the district measured and divided it into bighas and correct map was prepared for every village. Revised valuation of revenue was introduced in every Tehsils and Tehsils were divided into various assessment circles with reference to the source of irrigation, the system of agriculture and other circumstances. In this settlement summary the riverine areas were also included as Bet Sindh and Bet Chenab circles together, with the chahi sailabi circle where placed to be unsteady system assessment, where by the cultivated areas measured annually and imposed revenue per acre was fixed for each village. Beside it the first regular settlement was carried out many other systems which were new for people such as department of canal management and revenue department was introduced. The work of these departments was arrangements for future relief of estate in the case of failure of canal irrigation system. Through this summary settlement many agricultural zones had received relief by the introduction of variable system.³¹

The 2nd Regular Settlement Summary:

This settlement was headed by Pandit Harikishan khal, p.c.s, in the three southern Tehsils of the District Muzaffargarh in the year between 1900-1920. In the Layyah Tehsil work was inspected by Captain Crosthwaite but unfortunately he was died before compilation of his work. So, in the Layyah Tehsil Harikishan nath to conduct his work. He adopted three methods of assessment. First was the Thal assessment. Well was the unit of cultivation in the Thal area, there were different wells worked together in groups, in this case their assessment was not possible, so first he formed them into an estate and then assessed them separately. This was a method of Diwan sawn mal which was adopted by British with sum amendments. Waste land area like grazing land riverine land also assessed. And relief to be given in bad years as in flood and another natural disaster but in practice the demands had always been easily paid.

2nd was the assessment of canal secure estates. Mr. O, Brien imposed fix assessment on thos lands which was secure from the floods and was maintained by his successor in the pakka and Thal circle of the Muzaffargarh tehsil, and in the pakka and Nehri Thal circle of Kot Adu Tehsil, he changed it in Alipur except in part of three estates.

The assessment was first estimated for each estate, 2nd holdings were graded the number of those holdings depending on the circumstances of the each estate. The rates were then fixed for each estate with their help the revenue was imposed over the holdings. Wells which had been sunk after the first settlement were given to remission of the difference between Nehri and chahi nehri rates up to a period of 20 years.

The water tax ten annas per-acre. The canal irrigated lands of the Ali Pur had placed under fixed assessment by Mr. O. Brien. But Harikishan Kual assessed them again and put them in riverine tract, and maintained the fixed assessment those areas were surrounded the towns of Ali Pur Jatoi and Sher sultan and in secure portions of the Chenab and Indus circles. The rates of crops were fixed and rules were framed for the wells whom were under repair and brought them into use³².

The 3rd Regular Settlement Summary.

The third regular settlement was headed by Mr. J. d Anderson, I.C.S, from the year 1921 to 1925. These settlements based on operation of works relating to the revision of the previous records, re-measurement of Thal, re-measurement of flooded areas and secure areas.

Re-corrections of maps, record of rights and village note books were carried out. There was no major change had been seen in the 3rd regular settlement except it that the chahi sailabi circle of Ali Pur had been abolished and pakka circle of Muzaffargarh Tehsil had been sub divided into two parts Mustaqil and gair Mustaqil?

The soil division had been done on the base of irrigation. The small revenue which was imposed on wells was abolished and revenue on rate of crops had been introduced in the whole of the district except Thal. The mustaqil part of pakka had been retained under the fixed assessment.

In the first settlement was measured up in squares system on account of vast size. Its sandy hills and hardships were under gone in the desert by the surveyors, the instrument was used it was very inaccurate. In the last settlement those expensive and useless labor was not again used. Only those areas of land were measured, which were round the wells. For the purpose

of measurement the district divided into three parts. First the riverine areas and a few canal estates those were mapped inaccurately because of natural difficulties.

2nd were the canal villages in which here had been little change since the settlement and old maps accurate in those maps correction could be carried out quickly. And the great waste land of the Thal which had no any satisfactory map. So its measurement was important for practical purposes³³. The total assessment was 726477 on the District level. under these settlements the revenue of the tehsils to fluctuate year to year. AS the period of remission of new wells expired and canal irrigation was extended. In the last year of old settlement the assessment of date revenue and malkana to reject.

History of Land Revenue system

In the subcontinent land revenue has always circulated in different forms. In the sultanate period ruler had right to share the income of the land from the cultivators. Sher Shah Suri was the first ruler who was introduced land revenue system. During his time lands measured and divided them into bighas and fixed land revenue. There were two kinds of revenue one was batai—charged at the rate of one fourth of total land, 2nd was the zabat in this form of revenue charged at nature of land. He introduced revenue officers as Patwaris, Qanoongo, karkun, all worked in each sarkar under the supervision of Subehdar, and Subehdar was overall in charge of each sarkar. During the Mughals rule, Akbar was the first ruler who introduced the system of fixation of land revenue first time in the proper form of regular settlement in 1574. In those days the record was prepared in the Jmabandi form and the term of settlement was fixed for ten years. By this system the cultivator was responsible first to pay the state and then he estimated his expenditures. During the course of this settlement land revenue was assessed on the land class wise, an Amil (collector) was appointed in each sarkar. During the Sikh rule district was united under Diwan Sawan Mal rule, who imposed many taxes on land produce. One kind of tax was Nazar Makhdumi, it was taken when crops production was good and a shukrana fee was taken when crop rates were increased by their fix rates. Nazar mohrrir was imposed when crops weighted, fruit korawa was taken from cattle watch men.³⁴ Later on this system was adopted by British rulers with some necessary amendments and then imposed it in the whole Punjab. The economic development can be seen in the British rule, the revenue system totally changed by the British. They finished all previous taxes. During British rule the major development was their policy of settlement. They made three settlements in the district Muzaffargarh.³⁵

Under these settlements the first concern of the state was taken revenues. Their land revenue demands were very high, the kinds of revenues as chehr revenue and rakh revenue, chehr imposed on canals and rakh imposed on wells. Through these land taxes government collected lot of money annually. Their land revenue system based on actual outruns and actual prices. All those persons who were connected with land were fully inquired. Their check and balance system is very good through this system they maintained the economy of the country. This was a good step towards the economic development taken by British government. They established here revenue department in every district, its head was deputy commissioner. Tehsildar, Zaildar Patwarries and Lamberdars and Sofaidposh were also worked under revenue department, and their duty was to collect the revenues and to save the record of lands.

The first source of earning income of the British Government was land revenue for this purpose they made list of ordinary cultivators and list of those persons was arranged they belong to elite class who received land from ruler of the time like Kabul, Sindh and Delhi; government imposed tax on them, they were the Syeds, Qureshes and Pathan, Arain and Rajpoots. They registered those persons who occupied land by private arrangements, they categorized as; Mundimaar, Adhalpi and Bootamaar tenants. They finished private revenue agents like Hindu Merchant, and exploiters. In third settlement a new class of land revenue workers as Inamdars they were the operators of shamalat land and later on they have to right purchase the shamalat land. In the 1887 the tenancy act introduced and through this act tenants received little protection.³⁶

These are the kind of Village tenures in the Tehsil Ali Pur as;

Bhayyachara Mukammal and Bhayyachara ghair Muakammal, Zamindari and patedari, Zamindari was rare in the Tehsil and pata Dari and Bhayyachara Mukammal was at small level in 1960. Bhayyachara was at common in the Tehsil Ali Pur because the large area of land was consisting on riverine tract.³⁷

Land Revenue	Grazing Revenue	Total	Net Assests	Total
205780	----	205738	308010	219738

Land Revenue in the District Muzaffargarh;

Year	Land Revenue	Abiana
1952	25945	211539
1953	29446	118479
1954	33406	230599
1955		319012
1956		61812
1957		705735
1958		1846218
1960		1685388

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